

Psychological Safety	<p>Do the employees have to/need to work overtime, regardless of whether this is formally tracked in work time sheets or not?</p> <p>Are employee engagement surveys being conducted?</p> <p>*Are the practices, methods and indicators related to employee engagement and overtime aligned between teams?</p>
Effective Communication	<p>Does the organization provide an online communication tool/platform for intra unit communication and information exchange for its employees?</p> <p>Does the organization conduct context sharing/background sharing/alignment events for informing unit members' on each others' work?</p> <p>*Does the organization conduct context sharing/background sharing/alignment events for informing different units' members' on each others' work?</p>
Unit Autonomy and Empowerment	<p>Does the organization enable feature teams or similar organizational formations?</p> <p>Does the organization communicate the importance and potential impact of decentral decision making to its employees?</p>
Unit Collaboration	<p>Does the unit have a multi-stakeholder project setup among the unit members?</p> <p>Does the organization communicate the importance and potential impact of implementing interdisciplinary projects to its employees?</p> <p>*Does the organization have a multi-stakeholder project setup across different units?</p>
Personal Growth	<p>Does the organization provide an online learning platform of its own, or an organizational access to any of the existing online learning platforms for its</p> <p>Do the team members have any established learning targets?</p> <p>Do you support your employees to participate in employee trainings?</p>
<p><i>*Indicates a question that is asked for the product development scale</i></p>	